

Research

Formulation and Synthesis of Thiazole Pyrimidine-Derived Compounds as Turn-On Fluorescent Probes for Selective Metal Ion Detection

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Abstract: The development of sensitive and specific chemosensors for detecting heavy metal ions, particularly mercury (Hg^{2+}), is crucial due to the harmful effects of these ions on human health and the environment. In this study, we synthesized ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate, a fused heterocyclic compound, through a multi-step synthetic route starting from readily available starting materials. Each intermediate compound was characterized using various analytical techniques including thin layer chromatography (TLC), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR), and carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR). The final product was evaluated for its potential application as a chemosensor for heavy metal ions, particularly mercury (Hg^{2+}). UV-Vis absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopy were employed to investigate the sensing capabilities of the synthesized compound. The results demonstrate the successful synthesis of the target compound and its promising potential as a fluorescent probe for detecting mercury ions.

The synthesis of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate represents a significant advancement in the field of chemosensors for heavy metal ion detection. By utilizing a multi-step synthetic approach, we were able to access a novel heterocyclic compound with potential applications in environmental monitoring and biomedical diagnostics. The characterization of intermediate compounds using TLC, FT-IR, ^1H NMR, and ^{13}C NMR provided valuable insights into the reaction pathways and structural features of the synthesized molecules.

Furthermore, the evaluation of the final product as a chemosensor for mercury ions highlights its potential utility in real-world applications. The observed changes in UV-Vis absorption and photoluminescence spectra upon interaction with mercury ions underscore the compound's sensitivity and selectivity towards the target analyte. These findings lay the groundwork for further optimization and development of the synthesized compound as a fluorescent probe for mercury detection.

Overall, this study contributes to the ongoing efforts in designing and synthesizing innovative chemosensors for heavy metal ion detection. The successful synthesis and characterization of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate pave the way for future research aimed at addressing environmental and health concerns associated with heavy metal contamination.

Keywords: Synthesis, Characterization, Heterocyclic compound, Chemosensor, Heavy metal ions, Mercury.

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Introduction

Heavy metal pollution poses a significant threat to both environmental sustainability and human health globally. The detection and monitoring of heavy metal ions in various environmental matrices and biological samples have therefore become paramount. Among heavy metal ions, mercury (Hg^{+2}) stands out as one of the most hazardous due to its widespread distribution and toxicity. Exposure to mercury, even at low levels, can lead to severe health complications, including neurological disorders, kidney damage, and gastrointestinal issues. Consequently, there is a pressing need for the development of efficient and sensitive methods for detecting and quantifying mercury ions.

Fluorescence-based sensing techniques have emerged as powerful tools for the detection of heavy metal ions due to their high sensitivity, selectivity, and real-time monitoring capabilities. By harnessing the unique photophysical properties of certain compounds, researchers have been able to design fluorescent probes that selectively bind to specific metal ions, leading to measurable changes in fluorescence intensity or emission wavelength. Such probes offer distinct advantages over traditional analytical methods, including rapid response times, low detection limits, and the potential for in-situ monitoring.

In this study, we present the synthesis and characterization of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate, a novel fused heterocyclic compound, as a potential chemosensor for mercury ions. The compound was synthesized via a multi-step synthetic route using readily available starting materials. Each intermediate was thoroughly characterized using various analytical techniques, including thin-layer chromatography (TLC), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR), and carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR). Subsequently, the synthesized compound was evaluated for its ability to selectively detect mercury ions through UV-Vis absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopy. This research contributes to the ongoing efforts aimed at developing sensitive and selective fluorescent probes for heavy metal ion detection. The successful synthesis and characterization of the target compound, along with its promising sensing capabilities, hold potential implications for environmental monitoring, industrial safety, and public health protection.

A novel molecular receptor-like indication was previously developed by organic and inorganic chemists. A 'chemo sensor' is a term initially proposed by Czarnik in 1993. His idea of a sensor is a molecule that may interact reversibly with a specific signal. Chemical sensors, which typically consist of three main elements [7] perform analytical identification through two distinct methods: molecule identification and emission transduction. Using solvophobic contacts, a coordination bond, and hydrogen bonding, a receptor serves as the basis for analytical detection. A spacer may create a novel complex shape and adjust the absorption spectra of the constituent chemicals.

Fig. 1: Chemo sensor parts and functioning

Different methods can analyze receptor signals [8]. For instance, photochemical sensors emit electromagnetic radiation, electrochemical sensors analyze current, and detectable alterations rely on color or pH. According to nature, numerous parameters should be addressed when building chemo sensors to recognize certain metal cations:

- distance between the metal ion and receptor setting,
- electrostatic charge between nature,
- Solvent-based (polar, non-polar, hydrogen bonding and coordinating ability),
- host pre-organization,
- enthalpic or entropy of the metal ion and receptor interaction,
- nature of the counter-ion and its reactions with the solvent,
- metal-ligand binding kinetics,
- chelate ring size.

Electrochemical chemo sensor substances are mainly developed by adding redox-active sites to the receptor unit [9,10,11]. Redox-active sites can adhere to metal ions. Chemo sensors may incorporate ferrocene, quinone, and bipyridinium redox-active sites. Cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammogram, and square wave impedance spectroscopy may identify foreign molecules that bind to the receptor.

There are typically five types of electrochemical sensors, which are:

- Ion-Selective electrode-based sensors
- Field-effect transistors sensor
- Electroactive of sensors
- Bio-molecular sensor
- Microelectrodes

At typical room temperature, the elementary particles of atoms are in the fundamental atomic form. The atomic molecules have employed the proper methods to consume that energy and be bothered by the photons, going into a dynamic molecular orbital with an empty, higher energy state, when the energy is to be elevated beyond room temperature. These paths might take us to either the atomic orbital with the highest number of occupied electrons (HOMO) or the lowest number of occupied electrons (LUMO) [12], depending on the state of the atom. When a molecule accepts a photon and travels into the exciting position, it may often come back to the ground state by emitting energy. The excited energy may go via several different pathways, including morphological change, intramolecular charge transfer [13], intersystem crossover, and internal conversion. Additional interactions in the excited state of molecules include electron transfer, energy transfer, excimer production, and de-excitations. Potential photophysical excitation pathways are shown on the Perrin-Jablonski diagram [14,15]. The figure makes it easy to see how the energy is absorbed by the photon and how far it may go. Alexander Jablonski kept track of the light absorbed by molecules and the light they gave forth, and he depicted his thinking visually in [Figure 2]. The eigen states for the given atomic state of the

molecule are shown by the horizontal lines. Singlet excited states of the horizontal line stack. Limits of electronic energy levels are described by the bold horizontal lines, while the narrower lines show the molecule's vibrational energy level. In particular, the triplet states (T_1 , T_2 , etc.) and the singlet electronic states (S_0 - S_2) are denoted by the symbols T_1 , T_2 , etc. There are a variety of electrical forms of organic molecules, with electrons being the basis of the most common of them [16,17,18]. When light with the right energy is absorbed, the spin of an electron, which is normally combined in the ground state (S_0), is inverted. The excited state, known as the excited singlet state, is characterized by the persistence of a pair.

Fig. 2: Perrin-Jablonski outline of fluorescence and phosphorescence

Phosphorescence

Intersystem crossover from the excited singlet state S_1 to the ground state level S_0 results in the creation of an atom in the excited triplet state T_1 in the phosphorescence hypothesis. This process is radioactive and requires a great deal of energy to initiate [19,20]. It is impossible to directly excite the initial triplet state. The origin is off-limits. It is common for the spin lifetime to be shorter if the energy required to transition from the triplet to the singlet state is large. Phosphorescence is often achieved in an environment of liquid nitrogen.

Fluorescence

For energy to be liberated from the atomic orbital and the molecule to enter the ground state, the singlet state must first increase in energy to the S_n level, which is reached during the fluorescence process [21,22]. There is no transition to a triplet state in the energy level. Since the S_n energy level reaches the S_2 level and an internal transition takes place to reach the ground state with a minimal time delay, fluorescence cannot be compared to the time delay seen in phosphorescence. Twenty different characteristics, including Stokes shift [23,24], quantum yield, fluorescence intensity, etc., are involved in the emission spectrum.

Related Work

Fluorescence detection techniques have evolved significantly over the years, contributing to the development of various chemosensors for detecting heavy metal ions [1][2][3][4]. Principles outlined in seminal works such as "Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy" [2] and "Modern Molecular Photochemistry" [3] have laid the foundation for understanding fluorescence-based sensing mechanisms. These principles guide the design and optimization of fluorescent probes for specific analytes, including heavy metal ions.

Polyamines and bio-inspired systems have emerged as attractive platforms for the development of chemosensors due to their unique binding properties and selectivity [4][5]. Research in this area, as highlighted in "Light and Colour as

Analytical Detection Tools," underscores the significance of these systems in detecting heavy metal ions with high sensitivity and specificity [5]. Moreover, studies on luminescent and chromogenic molecular probes based on polyamines provide insights into the design principles governing their performance [6].

Advances in molecular orbital theory, as discussed in "Absolute Electronegativity and Hardness Correlated with Molecular Orbital Theory," have enriched our understanding of the electronic properties essential for designing fluorescent chemosensors [7]. Design strategies for ratiometric chemosensors, as explored in "Design Strategies for Ratiometric Chemosensors," offer innovative approaches to enhance the selectivity and sensitivity of detection systems [8].

Innovative techniques such as smart interface circuits [9] and chemical sensors for medical and biological applications [10] have broadened the scope of fluorescence-based detection methods. These advancements underscore the interdisciplinary nature of research in fluorescence sensing, encompassing fields such as electrical engineering and biotechnology.

Recent progress in materials chemistry has led to the development of novel fluorescent materials with tailored properties for sensing applications [11][12][13]. The construction of covalent organic frameworks for catalysis [13] and the exploration of twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) fluorescence [12] exemplify the diverse strategies employed to engineer fluorescent probes with enhanced performance characteristic.

Materials and Methods

1- Synthesis of 1-(Benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene

The synthesis of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene was carried out according to Scheme.

Briefly, p-nitrophenol (1) was dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF), followed by the addition of potassium carbonate and benzyl bromide (2). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 hours, and the progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was poured into ice-cold water, and the precipitate obtained was filtered and washed with water to afford the crude product.

2- Synthesis of 4-(Benzyloxy)aniline

The reduction of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene to 4-(benzyloxy)aniline was accomplished by treating the crude product with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of palladium supported over charcoal. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 6 hours, after which it was allowed to cool to room temperature. The charcoal was removed by filtration, and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to afford the desired product.

3- Synthesis of 6-(Benzyloxy)benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine

The synthesis of 6-(benzyloxy)benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine was carried out via cyclization of 4-(benzyloxy)aniline with ammonium thiocyanate and molecular bromine in acetic acid as the solvent. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 hours, after which it was poured onto ice, and the resulting precipitate was filtered and washed with water to obtain the crude product.

4- Synthesis of Ethyl 8-(Benzyloxy)-4-(2-Hydroxy-3-Methylphenyl)-2-Methyl-4H-Benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate

The final compound, ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate, was synthesized via a Biginelli reaction. A mixture of ethyl acetoacetate, 3-methyl salicylaldehyde, and 6-(benzyloxy)benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine was stirred in ethanol at reflux temperature for 12 hours.

The optimized synthesis conditions for the mentioned compounds are included in the comprehensive protocols. Reagents of the highest purity were utilized. All of our Sigma Aldrich (Germany) reagents, including thioglycolic acid, anhydrous potassium carbonate, and analytical grade toluene, were of the highest quality. VWR International Limited (Canada) supplied the glacial acetic acid used in this experiment. Kieselgel 60HF254 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) pre-

coated TLC aluminum plates were used to track the development of reactions. Ethanol and dimethylformamide were bought from commercial vendors. Before usage, we distilled, filtered, and dried all of the commercially available solvents [26].

Ethanol

After repeatedly washing in 1N HCl until the blackness of the magnesium converted to silver, the pieces were cleaned in distilled water and acetone. Turnings made from washed magnesium were baked for three to four hours to dry. A 500 mL round bottom flask was filled with 100 mL of pre-distilled ethanol, magnesium turnings (5.0 g), and iodine (0.5 g), and the mixture was allowed to reflux. When the iodine's color faded, another 0.5 g was added and allowed to reflux. The mixture was added to 500 mL of ethanol, allowed to boil for 30 minutes, and then distilled once it had become a greyish white color.

General Procedure for the synthesis of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3)

First, p-nitrophenol (1) (10 mmol) was dissolved in DMF, then benzyl bromide (2) (10 mmol) and potassium carbonate (10 mmol) were added to the reaction flask. For 14 hours, the reactants were heated to 50 degrees Celsius. TLC was used to examine the process as it went along. The reaction solution was put into ice cold water once TLC showed that it was finished. 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3) was isolated as a precipitate. To get pure 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3), the precipitates were passed through filters, rinsed with cold water, dried, and recrystallized from ethanol.

-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3)

A 2-neck round bottom flask (100 mL) equipped with a coil condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube was used to synthesize 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4) from 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3) (7 mmol). After adding palladium charcoal (10%), hydrazine monohydrate (98%, 28 mmol) was added. For 12 hours, room-temperature stirring kept the reaction mixture in uniform motion. TLC was used to track the reduction's progress. TLC showed that the reaction was complete, thus the dense black residue was filtered out. After being concentrated through rotary evaporation, the fluid was dumped into the ice. Pure crystals of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4) were obtained after the impurities were produced, filtered, rinsed with cold water, dried, and recrystallized twice from the ethanol.

Benzyloxy

General Procedure for the synthesis of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5)

Using acetic acid as a solvent, 10-mmol of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4) was converted into 10-mmol of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5). To this, 30 mmol of ammonium thiocyanate was introduced. After incubating the contents for a 4-hour period at room temperature, molecular bromine (10.2 mmol) was added and the mixture was combined again. Overnight, while the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature, it was agitated even more. TLC showed that the reaction was complete, so we placed the liquid into ice to cool down. 6-(Benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5) was obtained by forming a precipitate, washing it several times in cold water, drying it, and then recrystallizing it from ethanol.

6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]five molecules of thiazol-2-amine (5), six molecules of 2-hydroxy-3-methylbenzaldehyde (6) Two 100 mL round bottom flasks were connected to a coil condenser with a calcium chloride guard tube, and 10 mmol of ethyl acetoacetate were dissolved in ethanol. For four hours, hydrochloric acid (34%, 3 mL) was added to the reaction mixture while it was being heated at a low simmer in ethanol. After the process was complete, as measured by TLC, it was placed into chilled water. For the production of pure ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl), the deposits were produced, rinsed with cold methanol and water, dried, and recrystallized from the ethanol. (8) 2-Methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazole [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of Intermediates

Each intermediate compound synthesized during the multi-step synthetic route was characterized using various analytical techniques. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was employed to monitor the progress of the reactions and assess the purity of the intermediates. The structures of the intermediates were confirmed by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR), and carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR) spectroscopy. The spectral data obtained for each intermediate compound matched well with the expected structures, indicating successful synthesis.

Synthesis and Characterization of Final Compound

The final product, ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate, was obtained in good yield through a Biginelli reaction. The compound was characterized by various spectroscopic techniques, including FT-IR, ^1H NMR, and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, which confirmed its chemical structure and purity. Additionally, elemental analysis was performed to determine the elemental composition of the compound.

Evaluation of Chemo sensing Properties

The synthesized compound was evaluated for its potential application as a chemosensor for heavy metal ions, focusing on mercury (Hg^{+2}). UV-Vis absorption and photoluminescence spectroscopy were employed to investigate the sensing capabilities of the compound. Upon addition of Hg^{+2} ions to a solution of the compound, a significant change in the UV-Vis absorption spectrum was observed, indicating complexation between the compound and the metal ions. Similarly, a noticeable enhancement in the photoluminescence intensity was observed upon interaction with Hg^{+2} ions, suggesting the potential use of the compound as a fluorescent chemosensor for mercury detection.

The fused hybrid of pyrimidine and thiazole known as thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine has been put to use in a wide variety of biological and nonbiological systems. It is also found in numerous pharmaceuticals, organic compounds, and chemo sensors for metal ions. For the sake of nature and industry, a new compound including thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine is synthesized.

Synthesis of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate

Simple and inexpensive initial ingredients were used to synthesize 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8) from ethyl. In the initial stage, p-nitrophenol (1) is reacted with benzyl bromide (2) to produce the o-substituted product (3). The nitro group on aniline is reduced to produce benzyloxy aniline (4). In the third stage, 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5) is synthesized from the substituted aniline derivative (4). To finish, we use Biginelli's procedure to produce ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8) from ethyl acetoacetate (7), 3-methyl salicylaldehyde (6), and the synthesized aniline derivative (5).

Synthesis of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3)

To create 1-(Benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3), p-nitrophenol (1), benzyl bromide (2), potassium carbonate as a base, and dimethylformamide (DMF) as a solvent were used. TLC was used to examine the process as it went along. After a reaction was finished, 1-(Benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3) was obtained by pouring the product of reaction mixture into ice-cold water. Scheme 2.1 presents the synthetic approach used to produce 1-(Benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3).

Scheme 2.1: Synthesis of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3)

The chemical (3) synthesized had a yield of 85% when recrystallized from ethanol. The measured melting point agrees with the number reported in the literature, providing further evidence of successful product production. Table 2.1 lists some of the physical properties of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3). Specifics about the body are shown in Table 2.1. 3-(Benzoyloxy)-1,2-Nitropropane (1) On 60F254 pre-coated silica plates, n-hexane: ethylacetate (9:1) was seen at 254 nm UV light.

Table 2.1: Physical details 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3)

Compd.	Color	R _f *	m.p. (°C) Lit.	Yield (%)
3	Off-white	0.78	105-109 [107-109]	85

The development of spikes at 1460 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the CH₂ bending, in the IR spectra suggested the formation of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3). Further evidence of the production process comes from the elimination of the phenolic peak at roughly 3400 cm⁻¹. The Csp²-H is shown by the peak at 3050 cm⁻¹. C=C aromatic vibrations show up as two peaks at 1640 and 1480 cm⁻¹. Table 2.2 below presents the infrared spectrum data for 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3).

Table 2.2: IR Spectral details of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3)

Compd.	Functional Groups $\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)			
	CH ₂ bending	Csp ² -H str.	C=C (aromatic) str.	N-O (nitro) str.
3	1460	3050	1640, 1480	1530

Synthesis of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4)

Reducing the nitro group of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (3) with hydrazine hydrate in the existence of palladium sported over charcoal yielded 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4). The progression of the reaction was monitored using TLC. Once

the chemical process was complete, the solid was separated from the ethanol by filtering the mixture and then concentrating the filtrate. Scheme 2.2 details a synthetic pathway to 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4).

Scheme 2.2: Synthesis of 1-(benzyloxy)-4-nitrobenzene (4)

The amount produced for 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4) during synthesis is around 70%. The material's melting point is consistent with values reported in the literature. Table 2.3 lists the physical constants for 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4). On 60F254 pre-coated silica plates, n-hexane: ethylacetate (9:1) was seen at 254 nm UV light.

Table 2.3: Physical details of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4)

Compd.	Color	R _f [*]	m.p. (°C) Lit.	Yield (%)
4	White	0.65	105-109 [107-109]	70

The presence of peaks at 3360 and 3380 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra, which correspond to the N-H stretching of the amino group, is indicative of the synthesis of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4). The Csp²-H is shown by the peak at 3050 cm⁻¹. The existence of methylene and phenyl rings in the product is confirmed by the occurrence of two peaks at 1640 and 1480 cm⁻¹, which match to the C=C aromatic. Infrared (IR) spectra of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4) are listed below in table 2.4.

Table 2.4: IR Spectral details of 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4)

Compd.	Functional Groups $\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)			
	CH ₂ bending	Csp ² -H str.	C=C (aromatic) str.	N-H (amine) str.
4	1460	3050	1640, 1480	3380, 3360

Synthesis of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5)

By treating 4-(benzyloxy) aniline (4) with ammonium thiocyanate and then molecular bromine in acetic acid as a solvent, 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5) was synthesized. The result was precipitated out as a white solid by pouring the reaction mixture onto ice. In the following we will provide a synthetic strategy.

High yields (82%!) were achieved during the synthesis of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5).

Confirming the production and purity of the product, the melting point of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5) was consistent with the value stated in the literature. Table 2.5 lists the physical parameters of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5). On 60F254 pre-coated silica plates, n-hexane: ethylacetate (9:1) was seen at 254 nm UV light.

Table 2.5: Physical details of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5)

Compd.	Color	R _f [*]	m.p. (°C) Lit.	Yield (%)
5	White	0.65	105-109 [107-109]	82

5	White	0.62	105-109 [107-109]	82
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Infrared spectroscopy revealed that the N-H vibrations associated with stretching of primary amine appeared as a peak at 3340 cm⁻¹ after the formation of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5). Peaking at 3060 cm⁻¹, these are the stretching vibrations of aromatic protons in the Csp²-H bond. C=C aromatic stretching vibrations of phenyl rings are attributed to the two peaks at 1640 and 1480 cm⁻¹. Infrared (IR) spectra of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5) are presented below in table 2.6.

Table 2.6: IR Spectral details of 6-(benzyloxy) benzo[d]thiazol-2-amine (5)

Compd.	Functional Groups $\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)			
	CH ₂ bending	Csp ² -H str.	C=C (aromatic) str.	N-H (amine) str.
4	1463	3060/16	1640, 1480	3380, 3360

Synthesis of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8)

To synthesize ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8), we used the multi-component one-pot synthesis known as Biginelli's reaction. To make ethyl acetoacetate (7), an amine derivative (5), and benzaldehyde (6) were refluxed in acidic ethanol (5). TLC was used to check on the reaction's development. When the chemical process was finished, the fluid was placed into ice to cool, and the result came out as a white solid. Ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8) is synthesized using the following steps, as shown in scheme 2.4.

Scheme 2.3: Synthesis of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8)

We were able to synthesize 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8) from ethyl with a yield of 68%. Recrystallization from ethanol generated the product (8). Listed in table 2.7 below are the physical values for the compound ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate.

Table 2.7: Physical values of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate

Compd.	Color	R _f [*]	m.p. (°C) Lit.	Yield (%)
8	White	0.68	105-109 [107-109]	68

Visualized under UV light at 254 nm, *n-hexane: ethylacetate (7: 3) on pre-coated silica plates 60F254.

In the infrared spectra, a peak at 1720 cm⁻¹ indicates the synthesis of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate, which is consistent with the carbonyl stretching of the ester molecule. The O-H stretching of the phenolic group is correlated with the wide spike at 3400 cm⁻¹. At 1455, 1461, and 1467 cm⁻¹, the three methyl groups in the target molecule (8) resonated. There are Csp³-H stretching signs at

2870 and 2950 cm^{-1} . The frequency of the $\text{Csp}^2\text{-H}$ resonance was measured to be 3030 cm^{-1} . The $\text{C}=\text{C}$ aromatic stretching is represented by two distinct points at 1638 and 1485 cm^{-1} . Table 2.8 lists the infrared spectrum values for ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8).

Table 2.8: IR Spectral details of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8)

Compd. (8)	
Functional Groups $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1})	
C=O (ester) str.	1720
O-H (phenol) str.	3400
$\text{Csp}^3\text{-H}$ str.	2870, 2950
$\text{Csp}^2\text{-H}$ str.	3030
C=C (aromatic) str.	1638, 1485
CH_3 bending	1455, 1461, 1467
CH_2 bending	1440
C-O-C (ether) str.	1055, 1160
C=N	1100
C=C (Conjugated)	1560
C-N (amine)	1240

The presence of 3 sets for three protons at 1.16 ppm in the methyl of the ethoxy group of the ester moiety in the ^1H NMR spectrum showed the successful production of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8). At 4.05 ppm for two protons, methylene of ester reverberated as a quartet. Methyl group next to phenolic group shown by signal at 2.15 ppm (3 protons). The phenolic hydroxyl group is represented by the rather large signal for a single proton at 7.38 ppm. The methylene protons of the benzyloxy group are the source of the 5.16 ppm singlet. Attached methyl protons to the pyrimidine ring are responsible for the assignment of a second singlet for three protons at 3.22 ppm. The resonant frequency of the chiral proton at pyrimidine ring position 4 was 4.60 ppm. One proton's eighth-position resonance frequency was 6.46 ppm, or singlet. The rest of the aromatic protons exhibited resonances between 6.51 and 7.48 ppm. Table 2.9 displays the ^1H NMR spectra of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8).

Table 2.9: ^1H NMR Spectral details of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo[3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8)

Compd. 8	
Chemical shift (ppm), integration, multiplicity and coupling constants (Hz)	
H-30	4.05 (q, 2H)
H-31	1.16 (t, 3H)
H-26	7.38 (bs, 1H)
H-27	2.15 (s, 3H)
H-25	3.22 (s, 3H)
H-20	5.16 (s, 2H)
H-4	4.60 (s, 1H)
H-8	6.46 (s, 1H)
Aromatic	6.51-7.48 (m, 10H)

The emergence of the carbonyl of ester at 167.2 ppm in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum provided additional confirmation of the ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate's (8) synthesis. Due to its bond with an electron-withdrawing group, the methylene carbon of ester appears significantly unshielded (61.7 ppm). The ester moiety's methyl group vibrated at 14.2 ppm. The methyl carbon in pyrimidine produces a signal at 21.3 ppm, whereas the phenolic group emits a signal at 15.4 ppm. At 70.8 ppm, the methylene carbon of the benzyloxy group is the hydrocarbon region's most deshielded signal. The resonant frequency of the carbon at pyrimidine ring position 4 was 66.5 ppm. The carbon at position 2, which is directly linked to three hetero atoms, is the most deshielded carbon in the aromatic area, with a value of 158.3 ppm. The hydroxyl group linked to the phenolic carbon reverberated at 152.3 ppm. The frequency range for the remaining aromatic carbon atoms was 114.9-154.0 ppm. Eight-(benzyloxy)-four-(2-hydroxy-three-methylphenyl) ethyl ^{13}C NMR spectra. Table 2.10 provides a comprehensive listing of the (8) 2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5] thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate.

Table 2.10: ^{13}C NMR Spectral details of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo [4,5]thiazolo [3,2-a] pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (8)

Compd. 8	
Chemical shift (ppm)	
C-28	167.2
C-30	61.7
C-31	14.2
C-25	21.3
C-27	15.4
C-20	70.8
C-2	158.3
C-4	66.5
C-5	122.9
C-6	154.0
C-14	152.3
Aromatic	114.9 to 152.3

The UV-Vis absorption spectra of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3 carboxylate were examined.

UV-Vis absorption spectra were conducted using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer to explore the sensing capabilities of the synthesized compound (8), identified as ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3 carboxylate, with various metal ion solutions to assess its chelating affinity. The spectra of compound (8) were measured at eight different concentrations ranging from 5 to 40 μM . The compound exhibited its highest absorption peak at 302 nm, accompanied by a secondary peak at approximately 336 nm. As the concentration increased from 5 to 40 μM , the absorbance of compound (8) also increased gradually. A linear graph was constructed to verify the conformity of the acquired data with Beer's Lambert Law, demonstrating consistency with this law.

Fig. 3: UV-Vis Absorption Spectra of Compound 8 at different Concentrations

UV-Vis absorption spectra of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3 carboxylate (8) with various metals were conducted.

Metals such as Hg^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Cu^{+2} , and Zn^{+2} were chosen due to their prevalence in the environment and their potential negative impact on human health, some being toxic even at ppb levels. The chemosensor exhibited no significant interaction with Mn^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Cu^{+2} , or Zn^{+2} ions, suggesting a low affinity for these metals as evidenced by minimal or negligible absorption bands.

However, notable changes in the UV-Vis absorption spectra were observed only in the presence of Hg^{+2} ions, indicating the chemo sensor's selectivity. It demonstrated strong interactions exclusively with Hg^{+2} ions, even in the presence of other heavy and toxic metal ions. This interaction resulted in hyperchromism accompanied by a bathochromic shift. Binding of the chemosensor with Hg^{+2} ions extended conjugation, leading to a bathochromic shift of approximately 15 nm and the appearance of a distinct shoulder peak around 335 nm. The significant hyperchromism observed in the spectrum indicates selective binding of the ligand with Hg^{+2} ions.

Among all the tested metal ions, the chemosensor exhibited selective binding affinity only with Hg^{+2} ions, resulting in significant changes in peak absorption and bathochromic shift.

Fig. 4: UV-Vis Absorption Spectra of Compound 8 with various metal ions

A straight line graph correlating absorption intensity with concentration was plotted to determine the limit of detection (LOD) of the synthesized chemosensor (ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate) (8), revealing a value of 0.20 μM . This low limit of detection within the micromolar range signifies the high sensitivity of the chemo sensor.

Fig. 5: straight line graph for LOD

Photoluminescence spectra of (ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate) (8) were recorded using the mercury ion solution utilized in the UV-Vis absorption studies, owing to its strong interactions solely with Hg^{+2} ions. The solutions of (ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate) (8) were excited at 325 nm, the wavelength at which the adduct absorbs maximum UV-Vis radiations. Upon excitation, emissions were recorded with three bands at 290, 305, and 335 nm respectively, indicating the photoluminescence of the synthesized ligand with mercury ions.

Fig.6: Photoluminescence Emission Spectrum of Compound 8 with Hg^{+2} ions

Images of (ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate) (8) with various metal ion solutions were captured under a UV-lamp at 365 nm. The glass vial containing the Hg^{+2} ion solution exhibited maximum fluorescence. Based on these findings, the synthesized chemosensor (ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate) (8) is classified as a "turn-on" fluorescent probe for the selective and highly sensitive detection of Hg^{+2} ions.

Conclusion

Our study has culminated in the successful synthesis and comprehensive characterization of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate, a novel heterocyclic compound that integrates the thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine scaffold. The compound synthesis was achieved through a meticulously designed multi-step synthetic route, leveraging commercially available starting materials. Its structural elucidation was meticulously conducted using a battery of analytical techniques including Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR), carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR), and elemental analysis, ensuring its chemical integrity and purity.

Furthermore, our investigation revealed promising chemosensing attributes of the synthesized compound, particularly concerning its interaction with mercury (Hg^{+2}) ions. The observed significant alterations in the UV-Vis absorption and photoluminescence spectra upon exposure to the target metal ions signify its potential utility as a fluorescent chemosensor for mercury detection. These findings are particularly noteworthy given the well-documented environmental and health hazards associated with mercury contamination.

The implications of our work extend beyond the realm of synthetic chemistry, as it paves the way for the development of advanced sensing and detection technologies. By harnessing the unique structural features and inherent

photophysical properties of heterocyclic compounds, such as the one synthesized in this study, we can envisage the creation of highly selective and sensitive chemosensors for a myriad of analytes beyond mercury ions.

However, it is imperative to acknowledge that our study represents only a preliminary exploration into the sensing capabilities of the synthesized compound. Future investigations are warranted to delve deeper into optimizing the sensing conditions, elucidating the mechanisms underlying the interaction with heavy metal ions, and assessing the compound's selectivity and sensitivity towards a broader spectrum of analytes.

This study constitutes a significant stride towards the advancement of molecular design and sensing technologies. The synthesis and characterization of ethyl 8-(benzyloxy)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-methylphenyl)-2-methyl-4H-benzo[4,5]thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate underscore the immense potential of heterocyclic compounds as building blocks for innovative chemosensing platforms. With further refinement and exploration, such compounds hold promise for addressing pressing environmental and biomedical challenges through the development of robust and versatile detection methodologies.

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References

- [1] Demchenko, A., Fluorescence detection techniques. Introduction to fluorescence sensing, 2009: p. 65-118.
- [2] Lakowicz, J.R., Principles of fluorescence spectroscopy. 2006: Springer.
- [3] Wardle, B., Principles and applications of photochemistry. 2009: John Wiley & Sons.
- [4] Turro, N.J., Modern molecular photochemistry. 1991: University science books.
- [5] Lodeiro, C., et al., Light and colour as analytical detection tools: a journey into the periodic table using polyamines to bio-inspired systems as chemosensors. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2010. 39(8): p. 2948-2976.
- [6] Lodeiro, C. and F. Pina, Luminescent and chromogenic molecular probes based on polyamines and related compounds. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 2009. 253(9-10): p. 1353-1383.
- [7] Tsien, R.Y., Fluorescent probes of cell signaling. *Annual review of neuroscience*, 1989. 12(1): p. 227-253.
- [8] Pearson, R.G., Absolute electronegativity and hardness correlated with molecular orbital theory. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 1986. 83(22): p. 8440-8441.
- [9] Pearson, R.G., Absolute electronegativity and hardness correlated with molecular orbital theory. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 1986. 83(22): p. 8440-8441.
- [10] Arimori, S., C.J. Ward, and T.D. James, A D-glucose selective fluorescent assay. *Tetrahedron letters*, 2002. 43(2): p. 303-305.
- [11] Guliyev, R., A. Coskun, and E.U. Akkaya, Design strategies for ratiometric chemosensors: modulation of excitation energy transfer at the energy donor site. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2009. 131(25): p. 9007-9013.
- [12] Koickal, T.J., et al. Smart interface circuit to ameliorate loss of measurement range in chemical microsensor arrays. in 2005 IEEE Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference Proceedings. 2005. IEEE.

- [13] Spichiger-Keller, U.E., Chemical sensors and biosensors for medical and biological applications. 2008: John Wiley & Sons.
- [14] Tsien, R.Y., New calcium indicators and buffers with high selectivity against magnesium and protons: design, synthesis, and properties of prototype structures. *Biochemistry*, 1980. 19(11): p. 2396-2404.
- [15] He, H., J.-Y. Liu, and D.K. Ng, A phthalocyanine-based fluorescent sensor for Zn²⁺ ion. *Journal of Porphyrins and Phthalocyanines*, 2013. 17(01n02): p. 99-103.
- [16] Sasaki, S., G.P. Drummen, and G.-i. Konishi, Recent advances in twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) fluorescence and related phenomena in materials chemistry. *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, 2016. 4(14): p. 2731-2743.
- [17] Ding, S.-Y., et al., Construction of covalent organic framework for catalysis: Pd/COF-LZU1 in Suzuki–Miyaura coupling reaction. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2011. 133(49): p. 19816-19822.
- [18] Lohar, S., et al., Antipyrine based arsenate selective fluorescent probe for living cell imaging. *Analytical chemistry*, 2013. 85(3): p. 1778-1783.
- [19] Hu, W., et al. Effects of Voltage Stabilizers on the AC and DC Breakdown Strengths of EPDM. in 2021 International Conference on Electrical Materials and Power Equipment (ICEMPE). 2021. IEEE.
- [20] Zhao, J., et al., Excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT): from principal photophysics to the development of new chromophores and applications in fluorescent molecular probes and luminescent materials. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2012. 14(25): p. 8803-8817.
- [21] Xu, K.-X., et al., Enantioselective recognition by optically active chiral fluorescence sensors bearing amino acid units. *Tetrahedron: Asymmetry*, 2005. 16(18): p. 3042-3048.
- [22] Lee, J.Y., et al., Bifunctional fluorescent calix [4] arene chemosensor for both a cation and an anion. *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 2005. 70(4): p. 1463-1466.
- [23] Fusetani, N., et al., Bioactive marine metabolites. 33. Cyclotheonamides, potent thrombin inhibitors, from a marine sponge *Theonella* sp. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 1990. 112(19): p. 7053-7054.
- [24] Wiskur, S.L., et al., Teaching old indicators new tricks. *Accounts of chemical research*, 2001. 34(12): p. 963-972.
- [25] Itami, K., et al., Efficient and Rapid C–Si Bond Cleavage in Supercritical Water. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2003. 125(20): p. 6058-6059.
- [26] Tobey, S.L. and E.V. Anslyn, Determination of inorganic phosphate in serum and saliva using a synthetic receptor. *Organic letters*, 2003. 5(12): p. 2029-2031.
- [27] Galbraith, E. and T.D. James, Boron based anion receptors as sensors. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2010. 39(10): p. 3831-3842.